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Low-temperature catalytic methane splitting: a new reactor design for long-term hydrogen production --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	JFUE-D-24-09183R1
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	catalytic methane splitting; methane decomposition; COx-free hydrogen; filamentous carbon; reactor design
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Abstract:	<p>The low-temperature catalytic methane splitting, also known as methane decomposition, is expected to play a critical role in hydrogen production since it can use methane as in steam reforming but without carbon emissions. However, the production of solid carbon hinders the long-term stability of the catalytic process and its adoption as an industrially feasible technology. Until now, reactor designs such as fixed or fluidized beds did not overcome clogging and fast catalyst deactivation caused by carbon formation below 900°C. In this work, different reactor designs were tested to study their performance in terms of catalytic activity and stability. The use of thin and porous layers of a commercial Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst extended the catalytic stability from 1.8 h (using a fixed bed reactor) to 46.4 h (using a tubular coated reactor); corresponding to a production increase from 0.3 gC•gcat⁻¹ to 62 gC•gcat⁻¹, respectively. Carbon clogging and pressure build-up were avoided using a coated reactor containing catalytic substrates prepared by screen-printing and dip-coating techniques. The produced solid carbon was mainly filamentous. Therefore, the designed coated reactors displayed better stability, and if combined with interfacial cyclic carbon hydrogenation strategies to regenerate the catalyst, they are expected to be fully stable. The work provides a pathway for scaling up low-temperature catalytic methane splitting for large-scale deployment of dispatchable low-cost hydrogen production.</p>

Highlights

- Catalytic methane decomposition is a promising pathway for the energy transition;
- Carbon clogging causes pressure build-up in traditional reactor configurations;
- New concept for reactor design is presented – coated reactor;
- Reactor operation time is increased from 1.8 h to 46.4 h.

Low-temperature catalytic methane splitting: a new reactor design for long-term hydrogen production

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Abstract

The low-temperature catalytic methane splitting, also known as methane decomposition, is expected to play a critical role in hydrogen production since it can use methane as in steam reforming but without carbon emissions. However, the production of solid carbon hinders the long-term stability of the catalytic process and its adoption as an industrially feasible technology. Until now, reactor designs such as fixed or fluidized beds did not overcome clogging and fast catalyst deactivation caused by carbon formation below 900°C. In this work, different reactor designs were tested to study their performance in terms of catalytic activity and stability. The use of thin and porous layers of a commercial Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst extended the catalytic stability from 1.8 h (using a fixed bed reactor) to 46.4 h (using a tubular coated reactor); corresponding to a production increase from 0.3 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹ to 62 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹, respectively.

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23 produced solid carbon was mainly filamentous. Therefore, the designed coated reactors
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27 scale deployment of dispatchable low-cost hydrogen production.

28 *Keywords:* catalytic methane splitting, methane decomposition, CO_x-free hydrogen,
29 filamentous carbon, reactor design

30 Word count: 8760 words

31 **Abbreviations:**

32	CMS	catalytic methane splitting
33	CCS	carbon capture and storage
34	CCV	carbon capture and valorization
35	MS	methane splitting
36	NTP	normal temperature and pressure
37	TEM	transmission electron microscopy
38	TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
39	XRD	X-ray diffraction
40	GHSV	Gas hourly space velocity

41 **Nomenclature:**

42	α_{H_2}	hydrogen activity/production	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$
43	X_{CH_4}	methane conversion	%

44	\dot{m}_{H_2}	hydrogen mass flow	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$
45	W	catalyst mass	g_{cat}
46	ρ_{H_2}	hydrogen density at NTP conditions	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$
47	x_{H_2}	hydrogen molar fraction	
48	F_{out}	reactor outlet volume flow at NTP conditions	$\text{mL} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$
49	x_{CH_4}	methane molar fraction	
50	P	pressure	bar

51 **1. Introduction**

52 Currently, more than 95 % of the hydrogen produced worldwide comes from
53 reforming fossil-fuels, where steam methane reforming and coal gasification are the
54 most relevant ones [1]. The production of *grey* and *black hydrogen* alone accounts for
55 *ca.* 830 million tonnes of carbon dioxide emissions annually [2]. The transition towards
56 a hydrogen-based economy relies mostly on water electrolysis to produce the required
57 *green hydrogen*. However, there is a lack of installed capacity and storage
58 infrastructures for hydrogen. Moreover, the price of *green hydrogen* ranges from *ca.*
59 $3.4 \text{ €} \cdot \text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}^{-1}$ to $12 \text{ €} \cdot \text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}^{-1}$, depending on the source of renewable electricity, which is
60 not competitive when compared to the production costs of fossil hydrogen, of *ca.*
61 $1.0 - 3.0 \text{ €} \cdot \text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}^{-1}$ [1]. Another alternative is the implementation of carbon capture and
62 storage (CCS) or carbon capture and valorization (CCV) to produce *blue hydrogen*,
63 which may avoid the direct emissions associated with the current fossil-fuel-based
64 processes. Nevertheless, these technologies will increase the overall production costs,

65 and there are still safety issues related to CCS. In turn, the valorization of CO₂ into
66 added-value products is still too expensive and not mature enough [3].

67 In the current framework, methane splitting (MS), also known as methane
68 decomposition or pyrolysis, could enable soft and swift decarbonization since it can
69 deliver carbon-free hydrogen while benefiting from the infrastructures already
70 implemented for fossil fuels. Different sources of methane can be used, but biomethane
71 from biogas or other sources allows hydrogen production with an overall negative
72 carbon footprint.

73 This reaction occurs spontaneously at *ca.* 1300 °C. Still, it is possible to lower the
74 reaction temperature to 450 - 850 °C with catalysts, where nickel, iron, and cobalt have
75 been reported as the most active materials [4,5]. Since it is an equilibrium-limited
76 reaction, temperature plays a critical role in the conversion. Due to the endothermic
77 nature of the reaction, at 550 °C, the equilibrium conversion is *ca.* 52 %, while *ca.* 95 %
78 at 750 °C. Additionally, the equilibrium conversion decreases with the pressure [6].
79 Pressurization should only be considered if improves the separation of formed hydrogen
80 in one step without changing the pressure[7]. Even though there are reports of
81 secondary products in this process, the majority occurs when operation is done at higher
82 temperatures (> 1000 °C) or in the case of plasma technologies [4]. At lower
83 temperatures, the absence of secondary reactions simplifies the balance of the plant
84 since the only downstream process required is the separation of hydrogen from
85 unreacted methane [4].

86 The produced carbon has a wide range of potential high-value market applications,
87 such as electronically conductive paints, supercapacitors and batteries [8], fuel cells and
88 electrolyzers [9], but also for soil amendment [10], carbon-reinforced polymer
89 composites [11], carbon-reinforced concrete [12]. Considering all these benefits, the
90 price estimation of hydrogen from MS is between $1.70 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}^{-1}$ to $1.85 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}^{-1}$ [13–
91 15]. Therefore, this technology has great potential to be considerably cost-competitive
92 and faster to implement when compared to water electrolysis.

93 The main obstacle hindering industrial hydrogen production from low-temperature
94 catalytic methane splitting (CMS) is the inevitable carbon deposition at the catalyst
95 surface, which leads to its deactivation and reactor shutdown. Substantial efforts have
96 been made to develop catalysts with higher stability or reactor configurations that can
97 deal effectively with carbon production. Still, most processes rely on running the
98 process at very high temperatures, generally above 900 °C . Due to the increase in
99 importance of this process, there has been a large development of multiple processes to
100 make MS industrially feasible. BASF [16–18] developed a very high temperature
101 ($1200 \text{ °C} - 1400 \text{ °C}$) moving bed reactor, where seeding carbon particles are fed to the
102 reactor, flowing downwards, while methane is supplied from the bottom, and the
103 produced hydrogen is collected at the top of the reactor; MS plasma reactors have also
104 been proposed. Two variations of this process are thermal and non-thermal plasma.
105 Thermal plasma converts electric energy to thermal to reach very high temperatures.
106 Fulcheri and co-workers [19] recently reported the development of a thermal plasma
107 reactor, presently commercialized by Monolith; In non-thermal plasma, an ionized gas
108 is used to activate the MS reaction while maintaining the temperature relatively low;
109 approaches such as plasma-packed bed, corona discharge, or gliding-arc discharge have

110 been reported [20,21]; Molten metal bed reactors have recently received increasing
111 attention. MS is performed at temperatures $>1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a bubble column using low
112 melting point metals such as lead or tin. This type of reactor allows the separation of
113 the carbon materials by decantation and does not require catalysts [22,23]. Overall, for
114 operation of MS at high temperatures, there are still issues related with materials
115 capable of handling such temperature range and cheap energy sources must be used to
116 make the process economically viable.

117 Fixed-bed reactors are among the most commonly used designs for industrial
118 catalytic processes. However, their use for CMS is not possible because of the fast
119 carbon clogging of the bed. Fluidized-bed reactors are known to provide better mass
120 and heat transfer capabilities but also suffer from similar problems: carbon formation
121 changes the particle size and morphology in the catalytic bed and ultimately causes
122 defluidization and clogging [4,24]. In fact, the collision of particles during fluidization
123 was suggested to allow enough attrition to detach carbon by elutriation, but it was
124 shown to be ineffective [25]. Parmar and co-workers [26] studied the effect of
125 ultrasonication to remove carbon materials from the catalyst surface. Despite restoring
126 some catalytic activity during five cycles, the carbon separation yield was limited to
127 25 % to 50 %, thus requiring further oxidation to eliminate all the carbon. Apart from
128 the well-known fixed and fluidized bed reactors at low temperatures, small efforts have
129 been made to improve a stable catalytic reactor design. Most of the works focuses on
130 developing catalysts for high activity and/or stability [24]. Nickel, iron, and cobalt are
131 the most common metal catalysts for CMS; up to $650\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, nickel shows the highest
132 reported activities, while iron can be used at higher temperatures. The combination of
133 these two metals and/or other metals like copper or noble metals has been often reported

134 [4]. Wang and co-workers [27] reported the longest stability so far, with a lifetime of
 135 210 h at 650 °C with a customized Ni-Fe catalyst with a molar ratio of 2Ni:1Fe:1Al.
 136 The authors argued that the increased carbon diffusivity improved by the Fe is the
 137 reason for such stability. In fact, the balance between carbon formation and diffusion
 138 through the metal particles dictates the carbon materials formed[28] and the
 139 deactivation of the catalyst [29]. Table 1 showcases the most relevant results published
 140 in the last 2 years for supported nickel catalysts. However, it must be emphasized that
 141 most of the works reported were carried out in fixed-bed reactors where the catalyst is
 142 placed at the center of the reactor, with enough room for carbon growth. There is very
 143 little or no mention of reactor dimensions or reports of clogging.

144 Although avoiding catalyst deactivation is the primary objective for low-
 145 temperature CMS, developing suitable reactor designs for handling the carbon growth
 146 over the catalyst and carbon removal is essential. In this work, low-temperature CMS
 147 was conducted using a commercial catalyst of nickel supported on silica/alumina.
 148 Several coated reactor configurations were tested based on the immobilization of the
 149 catalyst in a layer while maintaining enough free space for carbon growth and removal.

150 Table 1 - Most relevant works in terms of activity and stability found in the literature
 151 in the last two years for single metal nickel-based catalysts

Ref	Catalyst		<i>T</i> (°C)	<i>t</i> (h)	Feed			Conversion (%)		Activity ($\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)			Carbon yield ($\text{g}_{\text{C}} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$)
	Catalyst	Amount (g)			Flowrate ($\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)	CH ₄ (vol.%)	GHSV ($\text{L} \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Initial	Final	Initial	Final	Average	
[30]	Ni/USY	0.02	600	60	40	22.5	120	66	57	3.17	2.76	2.97	534
[31]	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.01	550	32	20	100	100	14	3	2.50	0.54	1.52	146
[32]	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.6	600	30	50	95	5	35	0	0.30	0.00	0.15	13
[33]	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.01	750	10	20	50	100	58	0	5.18	0.00	2.59	78

[34]	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.01	550	20	20	100	100	18	4	3.28	0.65	1.96	118
[35]	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	0.01	550	24	20	100	100	17	11	3.04	1.96	2.50	180
[36]	Ni/LTA	0.05	500	22.5	30	40	36	32	10	0.82	0.26	0.54	36

152

153 2. Materials and methods

154 2.1 Catalytic Support Preparation

155 The 65 wt.% Ni supported on silica/alumina (Ni/SiO₂·Al₂O₃) was purchased from
 156 Sigma-Aldrich. The planar ceramic substrates Keralpor 99, with 35 mm diameter and
 157 1.5 mm thickness, 99.5 % alumina content, 0.36 – 0.38 porosity, and 1 μm average pore
 158 size, were purchased from Kerafol – Keramische Folien GmbH & Co. KG. These
 159 substrates were used to hold the catalyst, applied by screen-printing. The ink was
 160 prepared by mixing the catalyst powder and α-terpineol (Acros Organics, 301615000,
 161 CAS 98-55-5) in mass proportion of 70:30, respectively, using a Retsch PM100 ball
 162 miller for 1 h at 300 rpm, to obtain a homogeneous paste. The screen-printing was
 163 performed with a RokuPrint RP 2.2 screen-printer. The coated catalytic substrates were
 164 then dried for 10 h at 200 °C to remove the solvent and obtain a solid catalytic layer.

165 The catalyst was also applied over the internal surface of steel tubes and over the
 166 external surface of ceramic tubes by dip-coating. For the dip-coating, catalytic ink was
 167 obtained by mixing the catalyst particles with α-terpineol or ethylene glycol with a mass
 168 proportion varying from 10:90 to 30:70, respectively, and ball-milled for 1 h at 300 rpm
 169 to obtain a homogeneous emulsion. After the dip-coating procedure, using a dipping
 170 time of 10 s, the substrates were dried for 10 h at 200 °C under constant rotation to

171 obtain a uniform catalyst layer. Steel tubes of 9.5 mm outside diameter (o.d.) and
172 100 mm length were purchased from Swagelok. The assembly procedure for ceramic
173 tubular substrates is described elsewhere [37]. Briefly, a porous tubular substrate with
174 a 10 mm o.d. is connected to a non-porous ceramic tube using glass powder and thermal
175 treatment. The dip-coating of the catalyst is done only in the porous region. Before the
176 deposition, all the substrates were ultra-sonicated in diluted ethanol (50 vol.% water)
177 to remove surface impurities and then dried at 80 °C for 1 h.

178 2.2 Reactor design

179 Five different reactor configurations were constructed and used to study their
180 influence on the lifetime of the catalyst: I) fixed bed reactor, II) fluidized bed reactor,
181 III) wall coated reactor, IV) tubular coated reactor, and V) plate coated reactor. All
182 experiments were performed at 550 °C and 1 bar, and porous steel meshes were used at
183 each end of the reactor to prevent catalyst or carbon particles from escaping the reaction
184 zone, thus avoiding the clogging of the tubing. Methane (99.95 %), hydrogen
185 (99.999 %), and nitrogen (99.999 %) were used as feed, catalyst reduction, and purge
186 streams, respectively. Outlet stream compositions were analyzed using an online gas
187 chromatograph (Agilent 990Micro) equipped with a 10 m long Molsieve column and
188 using Ar as carrier gas and/or a mass spectrometer (Pfeiffer, Omnistar). In all
189 experiments, *in situ* reduction of the catalyst was achieved using 50 % of hydrogen
190 balanced with nitrogen, fed for 1 h. Afterward, nitrogen was fed for 30 min to purge the
191 reactor, and only then was the MS reaction started by feeding pure methane.

192

193 Figure 1 – Reactor configurations tested: I) fixed bed; II) fluidized bed; III) wall coated;
 194 IV) tubular coated; V) plate coated; a) reactor inlet/outlet; b) catalyst bed; c) glass
 195 beads; d) space for fluidization; e) catalyst layer; f) tubular substrate; g) planar
 196 substrate.

197 Table 2 - Main geometrical parameters of the tested reactor configurations

Reactor	Configuration	Diameter (cm)	Coating area (cm ²)	Volume (cm ³)
I	Fixed	0.95	n. a.	2.5
II	Fluidized	0.95	n. a.	5
III	Wall coated	0.95	20.9	5
IV	Tubular coated	2.5	15.7	31
V	Plate coated	1	5	5

198 n.a. – not applicable

199

200 All the reactors tested were schematized in Figure 1 and their main geometrical
201 parameters are shown in Table 2. The fixed and fluidized bed reactors, respectively
202 reactors I and II, were made of steel tubes with a diameter of 9.5 mm and a length of
203 70 mm. In the case of the fixed bed, glass beads (212-300 μm size) were used to fill the
204 volume gap between the catalyst bed and the reactor's entrance/exit. In the case of the
205 fluidized bed, the catalyst was placed at the bottom of the reactor to be fluidized. A
206 Coulter LS laser diffraction particle size analyzer was used to characterize the particle
207 size distribution of the supported catalyst and the Ergun equation was used to estimate
208 the minimum fluidization velocity and required flow rate. A wall coated reactor -
209 reactor III - was also assembled using the same steel tube as the previous reactors, where
210 the catalyst layer was deposited by dip-coating onto the inner wall (bore side) of the
211 reactor. Reactor IV is a tubular reactor with a porous ceramic tube loaded with the
212 supported catalyst on its external surface (shell side). The ensemble was inserted in a
213 steel tubular reactor with 30 mm o.d., 25 mm inside diameter and 400 mm length. The
214 non-porous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ tube can also act as feed to the inner part of the tubular substrate.
215 The last reactor, Reactor V, employs a planar ceramic substrate placed on the center of
216 a steel disc with a diameter of 80 mm. The disc was fit between two SAE310 steel plates
217 with 120 mm o.d., resulting in two individual chambers, with an equivalent diameter of
218 10 mm, separated by the catalytic substrate, with the catalytic layer facing downwards.
219 The reactor was sealed using Thermiculite[®] (Flexitallic) rings, and progressively higher
220 compression was applied until hermetic sealing was achieved. The experiments
221 performed with all reactor configurations are summarized in Table 3.

222 Table 3 - Summary of experimental parameters tested
223

Experiment Number	Reactor configuration	Feed flow rate (mL·min ⁻¹)	Catalyst mass (mg)	Catalyst loading (mg·cm ⁻²)	Space velocity (L·h ⁻¹ ·g ⁻¹)	Residence time (s)
1	Fixed bed (Reactor I)	10	500	n. a.	1.2	15
2	Fluidized bed (Reactor II)	20	500	n. a.	2.4	15
3	Wall coated (Reactor III)	20	500	23.9	2.4	15
4	Wall coated (Reactor III)	175	408	19.5	24.4	2
5	Wall coated (Reactor III)	175	235	11.2	41.5	2
6	Tubular coated (Reactor IV)	100	310	19.7	19.4	19
7	Tubular coated (Reactor IV)	125	266	16.9	28.2	15
8	Tubular coated (Reactor IV)	175	287	18.3	36.6	11
9	Tubular coated (Reactor IV)	175	165	10.5	63.6	11
10	Tubular coated (Reactor IV)	175	346	22.0	30.3	11
11	Plate coated (Reactor V)	50	39	7.8	76.9	6

224

225 The catalyst and the reactor were characterized using the catalytic activity (α_{H_2} ,
226 $g_{H_2} \cdot g_{cat}^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$) and the methane conversion (X_{CH_4} , %), computed using equations (2) and
227 (3), respectively.

$$\alpha_{H_2} = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2}}{W} = \frac{\rho_{H_2} x_{H_2} F_{out}}{W} \quad (2)$$

$$X_{CH_4} = \frac{F_{CH_4,0} - F_{CH_4}}{F_{CH_4,0}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

228 where \dot{m}_{H_2} is the hydrogen mass flowrate in $g_{H_2} \cdot h^{-1}$, W is the catalyst mass g_{cat} , ρ_{H_2} is
229 the hydrogen density at normal temperature and pressure (NTP) conditions in $g_{H_2} \cdot mL^{-1}$,
230 x_{H_2} is the hydrogen molar fraction, F_{out} is the reactor outlet volume flowrate at NTP

231 conditions in $\text{mL}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, $F_{\text{CH}_4,0}$ is the methane inlet volume flowrate at NTP conditions in
232 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and F_{CH_4} is the methane outlet volume flowrate at NTP conditions in $\text{mL}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.
233 Since the catalytic activity and conversion histories displayed a similar behavior, only
234 the catalytic activity is plotted; conversion plots can be found in Supplementary
235 Information (SI).

236 2.3 Morphological characterization

237 Samples of the catalytic layer were collected after each CMS experiment (*post-*
238 *mortem*). X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed using an X-ray
239 diffractometer from Rigaku SmartLab with a Cu K α radiation anode. Intensity data was
240 measured in a continuous mode through 2θ ranges between 15° and 80° with a step of
241 0.02° . Raman spectroscopy was performed on the produced carbon particles collected
242 and *post-mortem* catalytic layers, using a Witec alpha300, excited by a 532 nm laser.
243 Peak deconvolution was performed using a Lorentzian fitting function and the I_D/I_G
244 ratios were obtained using peak areas. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was
245 performed using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TG 209 F1 iris, Netzsch) under
246 $20 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of air flow, heating from room temperature to 900°C at a $5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The
247 morphology of the carbon materials was obtained by transmission electron microscopy
248 (TEM). A FEI QUANTA 400 FEG scanning electron microscope was used (FEI,
249 Hillsboro, OR, USA), equipped with an EDAX Genesys Energy Dispersive X-
250 Ray Spectroscopy (EDAX Inc., Mahwah, NJ, USA) microanalysis system. The
251 acceleration potential was kept at 15 keV while in-lens detector was employed with a
252 working distance of *ca.* 10 mm. For the analysis, BSE (Back-Scattered Electron) / SE

253 (Secondary Electron) modes were used. For EDS, a beam energy of 15 keV was used.
254 A JEOL 2200FS EF-TEM was used to bombard the samples with a 200 kV electron
255 beam and obtain the images.

256 **3. Results and discussion**

257 *3.1 Reactor Performance*

258 The catalytic experiments were first performed using conventional reactor
259 configurations: fixed and fluidized bed reactors (reactors I and II); both reactors were
260 loaded with 500 mg of the Ni-based supported catalyst, and the tests were performed at
261 550 °C. The feed flow rate was chosen so that the residence time was similar for all
262 reactor designs. The catalytic bed of the fixed bed reactor got clogged by carbon soon
263 after the start of the reaction, causing pressure build-up – Figure 2. The pressure of the
264 reactor remained stable for *ca.* 30 min, increasing to the point that the experiment had
265 to be stopped, *i.e.* until instant 2 h. The fluidized bed reactor operated for 4 h with stable
266 catalytic activity, after which the pressure increased quickly, and the reactor was
267 stopped. Since clogging was observed, the morphology and size of the catalyst particles
268 changed, causing defluidization. After opening the reactor, it was possible to observe
269 that clogging occurred at the bottom, after defluidization – Figure S4 in SI. Compared
270 to the fixed bed reactor, the longer operating time was mainly assigned to the available
271 space for carbon to grow. However, pressure build-up is inevitable after some time. So
272 far, most of the works reported in this field focus on the development of catalysts, and,
273 as such, catalytic characterization is performed in reactors with enough volume for the

274 catalyst to deactivate by carbon encapsulation and not by pressure build-up due to
 275 carbon clogging [4]. Carbon formation in these reactor configurations will inevitably
 276 clog the bed, blocking the inlet feed that will ultimately cause reactor shutdown to
 277 remove and/or substitute the catalyst bed.

279 Figure 2 – Variation of activity and pressure over time for the reactor configurations:
 280 a) fixed bed (Reactor I); b) fluidized bed (Reactor II), and c) wall coated (Reactor III),
 281 using 10, 20, and 20 mL·min⁻¹ methane feed at 550 °C, respectively.

282 In the wall coated reactor, reactor III, where the catalyst was deposited only in the
 283 inner wall of a steel tube, maximizing the reactor volume for carbon growth. In this
 284 reactor *ca.* 0.5 g_{cat} are deposited in a surface area of 20 cm² (*ca.* 23.9 mg_{cat}·cm⁻²).
 285 Catalytic activity and pressure (Experiment 3) as a function of the time-on-stream are
 286 also plotted in Figure 2. The reactor maintained an activity of *ca.* 0.1 g_{H₂}·g_{cat}⁻¹·h⁻¹ over
 287 11 h; during this period, no catalytic deactivation was observed. During the first 5 h of
 288 operation, the pressure did not increase, which was assigned to the large volume
 289 available for carbon growth. However, after that, pressure started increasing caused by
 290 carbon clogging of the reactor; the experiment was stopped with the pressure in the
 291 reactor reaching the feed pressure at instant 11 h. The absence of catalytic deactivation
 292 is a strong indication that methane was able to reach the active sites of the catalyst and

293 be converted into hydrogen and carbon. Overall, Experiment 3 produced 6 dm³_{NTP} of
294 hydrogen and 5 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹, which is considerably higher than that of the fixed bed
295 (0.53 dm³_{NTP}, 0.3 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹) and fluidized bed (2 dm³_{NTP}, 1.1 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹) reactors, which
296 used similar catalyst amount. The reactor was opened at the end of the experiment
297 (Figure 3), and it was observed to be completely full of carbon.

298

299 Figure 3 – Wall coated reactor (Reactor III) - *post-mortem*. Reactor clogged with
300 carbon.

301 To increase the amount of free volume available for carbon growth, the geometry
302 was inverted. In this case, the deposition was changed to the shell side, which was
303 encased in a larger tubular reactor. A closed alumina tube substrate was dip-coated with
304 the catalytic ink – reactor IV. The dip-coating of the substrate resulted in a layer
305 containing 0.266 g over an area of 15.7 cm² (17 mg_{cat}·cm⁻²). Using the same residence
306 time as for the previous configurations (Experiment 7), the reactor operated
307 continuously for *ca.* 21.5 h without any signs of catalyst clogging by carbon. The initial
308 activity was *ca.* 0.90 g_{H₂}·g_{cat}⁻¹·h⁻¹, and it started decaying after 3 h (Figure 4), most likely
309 due to carbon coverage of the active sites since no pressure build-up was observed. For

310 this reactor configuration, the pressure was not plotted since it remained stable at 1 bar
311 during the full experiment. Reactor IV – Experiment 7 produced *ca.* 46 dm³_{NTP} of
312 hydrogen and 13 g of carbon (47 g_C·g_{cat}⁻¹), and pressure build-up of the reactor for
313 accumulating the produced carbon was not the reason for the reactor's shutdown. The
314 decrease in catalyst activity was then assigned to the catalyst encapsulation with the
315 produced carbon. Figure S4g) in SI illustrates the carbon coating formed around the
316 catalyst layer, which was detached from the substrate. The detachment of the carbon
317 was mainly attributed to the poor adhesion of the catalytic film since no binders were
318 used. Morphological analysis of the *post-mortem* samples shows the presence of
319 catalyst agglomerates in the detached carbon – *cf.* Figure 8.

320

321 Figure 4 – Variation of activity over time for the tubular coated reactor (Reactor IV –
322 Experiment 7), using 125 mL·min⁻¹ methane feed at 550 °C. The pressure did not
323 increase in this reactor configuration.

324 Among the reactors tested, only Reactor IV reached catalyst deactivation without
325 pressure build-up. This was possible by reducing the amount of catalyst per unit of
326 volume. The amount of catalyst was decreased from 200 mg·cm⁻³ – Experiment 1, and

327 100 mg·cm⁻³ – Experiments 2 and 3, to 8.6 mg·cm⁻³ – Experiment 7; only Experiment
328 7 displayed no pressure drop until deactivation. All these experiments were performed
329 with the same residence time to allow comparing the conversion across all reactor
330 configurations; the reaction conversion was actually reasonably similar for all reactor
331 configurations. However, to have the same residence time, space velocity was
332 considerably increased in the tubular coated reactor (Reactor IV), which resulted in a
333 considerable increase in catalyst activity. Such an increase with no change in
334 conversion indicates that reaction equilibrium is affecting the reactor conversion. To
335 investigate this hypothesis further, several experiments were performed in the coated
336 configurations (Reactors III and IV); Figure 5 shows the activity and conversion of
337 Experiments 4 to 10. Experiments 4 and 5 were performed in the wall coated reactor
338 (Reactor III) using operating conditions similar to those of the experiments performed
339 using Reactor IV; the catalyst-to-reactor volume ratio was 82 mg·cm⁻³ and 47 mg·cm⁻³,
340 respectively. Low space for carbon accumulation led to a much earlier onset of pressure
341 build-up, leading to the interruption of both experiments just after 2 h, a much shorter
342 period when compared to Experiment 3 (11 h of operation). In all experiments, the total
343 amount of carbon produced was similar (*ca.* 2 g of carbon) since it was limited by the
344 volume of the reactor. Nevertheless, initial conversion was still close to 20 %, even
345 though the increase in the feed flow rate led to a residence time of just *ca.* 2 s. Similar
346 experiments were conducted using Reactor IV, where pressure build-up is not expected.
347 Experiments with different flow rates and similar catalyst loadings, and vice-versa,
348 were performed. In all experiments, initial conversion remained *ca.* 20 %, indicating
349 that reaction equilibrium is limiting the conversion of the reactor. However, the
350 equilibrium conversion for this reaction is *ca.* 52 %[6], *i.e.* higher than the conversion

351 observed. The endothermic nature of the reaction may play here a role, keeping the
 352 catalytic layer at a lower temperature compared to the temperature of the reactor.
 353 Structured reactors, such as the proposed configuration display an improved
 354 temperature homogeneity compared to conventional reactors [36]. However, a decrease
 355 in the temperature of 20 °C results in a decrease of the equilibrium conversion to less
 356 than 40 % [6] that, coupled with mass transfer limitations, should justify the observed
 357 conversion. Additionally, the observed conversions are similar to what is reported in
 358 the literature, with most of the experiments with pure methane feed having close to
 359 20 % conversions – *cf.* Table 1.

361 Figure 5 – Activity (top) and conversion (bottom) for several experiments: a)
 362 Reactor IV – feed flow rate; b) Reactor IV – catalyst loading; c) Reactor III –
 363 Experiment 4; d) Reactor III – Experiment 5.

364 Running a reaction close to equilibrium leads to catalyst underutilization; as
 365 displayed in Figure 5a) and b) increasing feed flowrate or decreasing catalyst loading
 366 leads to higher activity reaching *ca.* 2.5 $\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ – Experiment 9. Both operation

367 parameters determine the gas hourly space velocity (GHSV – methane volumetric feed
368 flowrate per gram of catalyst), which strongly affect the activity of the catalysts.
369 Increasing GHSV keeps product concentration around the film low and decreases mass
370 transfer limitations, leading to higher catalytic activities. However, increasing the
371 activity of the catalyst also accelerates deactivation. A higher carbon formation rate
372 hinders carbon diffusion through metal particles and accelerates deactivation.
373 Nevertheless, the normalized carbon production for all experiments using Reactor IV
374 was 62, 47, 48, 43, and 48 $\text{g}_C \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (Experiments 6 to 10, respectively), even though the
375 duration of each experiment was quite different, ranging from 8.8 h for Experiment 8
376 to 46.4 h for Experiment 6. The criteria to stop the experiments without pressure build-
377 up was set for a catalytic activity of *ca.* $0.15 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, *i.e.* below this value, the
378 experiment was stopped. All experiments displayed similar normalized carbon
379 production, with the highest carbon production corresponding to the lowest GHSV, and
380 vice-versa. Since carbon formation and diffusion play a critical role in catalyst stability,
381 lower GHSV values result in a lower catalytic activity, allowing carbon diffusion within
382 the metal catalyst particle to form more structured carbon materials maintaining the
383 catalyst active for a longer period. Additionally, since operational parameters can
384 influence the maximum carbon production of a catalyst, its optimization can lead to
385 catalyst lifetime increase.

386 To assess the maximum possible activity with the catalyst/reactor configuration, a
387 different coated configuration was tested employing a planar substrate. In this case,
388 Reactor V – plate coated reactor, uses a planar support loaded with the catalyst applied
389 by screen-printing as a homogeneous thin layer. The loading obtained was *ca.*
390 $7.8 \text{ mg}_{\text{cat}} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, the smallest loading used, close to the loadings used in the other coated

391 configurations. Nevertheless, the major difference compared with Reactor IV is the
392 smaller active area of this reactor, resulting in a considerably lower total catalyst
393 amount. However, the catalyst amount per unit volume of this reactor configuration
394 was maintained similar to the tubular coated configuration to avoid clogging, in this
395 case $7.8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. Experiment 11 uses a higher space velocity, maintaining a residence
396 time within the interval used in previous experiments (6 s). The objective was to assess
397 the reactor performance away from the reaction equilibrium concentrations. The
398 catalytic activity of this reactor is plotted in Figure 6. In this case, the initial conversion
399 of this reactor was just 7.1 %, indicating that equilibrium is not limiting the catalytic
400 activity. However, the catalytic activity is lower than for Experiment 9, where the
401 catalyst loading was $10.5 \text{ mg}_{\text{cat}}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, reasonably close to $7.8 \text{ mg}_{\text{cat}}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ of Experiment
402 11. Previous experiments showcased that residence times between 2 s and 19 s resulted
403 in conversions close to 20 %, and the residence time for this experiment is within this
404 range. An increase of *ca.* 20 % of the space velocity was sufficient to make the
405 conversion decrease considerably; this indicates that for these operating conditions, the
406 reaction is controlled by mass transfer limitations. With the catalyst being placed as a
407 film, it enables the formation of a boundary layer that can considerably decrease mass
408 transport to and from the catalyst hindering reaction kinetics. Additionally, this change
409 in the operational parameters accelerated considerably the deactivation, with the
410 catalyst becoming inactive after 2 hours of operation. This experiment produced only
411 $1.4 \text{ g}_{\text{C}}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$, a much lower amount when compared to Reactor IV experiments.
412 Increasing GHSV gives less time for carbon to diffuse through the metal catalyst
413 particle, which can change the mechanism of carbon formation and, consequently,
414 compromise the catalyst stability.

415

416 Figure 6 - Variation of activity over time for the plate coated reactor (Reactor V –
 417 Experiment 11), using $50 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ methane feed at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

418 Visual analysis of the *post-mortem* catalytic substrates showed the detachment of
 419 the catalytic layer from the substrate. *Post-mortem* catalytic substrates are displayed in
 420 SI, where the detachment of the catalytic layer is visible. In the case of Reactor IV, the
 421 catalytic substrate displayed a stable layer, but the formed carbon was detached from
 422 the substrate. On the other hand, Reactor V displayed severe layer detachment. The
 423 detached catalyst particles were fully covered by carbon, thus leading to the observed
 424 rapid deactivation. Particularly for the case of Reactor V, another additional reason for
 425 catalyst detachment from the substrate was the low mechanical stability of the thin layer
 426 caused by the reactor compression to reach hermetic sealing. Overall, in all coated
 427 reactor configurations, the detachment is also associated with poor adhesion between
 428 the catalyst and the support. The catalyst ink used in the screen-printing or dip-coating
 429 did not include any additives besides the catalyst powder and organic solvent. The use
 430 of a binder to increase the mechanical integrity of the film can play a key role in
 431 improving this reactor configuration. Additionally, optimization of the catalytic layer

432 in terms of loading and, consequently, thickness may improve carbon formation without
433 compromising the stability of the layer for long-term operation.

434 Table 4 summarizes the most relevant results. The results presented are very
435 comparable with the ones reported in the literature for low-temperature operation
436 ($< 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), with very few works surpassing the 30 h lifetime [4,38,39]. Considering the
437 results presented in Table 1, which reports the most promising works on monometallic
438 nickel catalysts published in the last two years, the results obtained in this work are
439 competitive, even though a commercial catalyst was used. Nevertheless, this work
440 focuses on assessing the role of the reactor design in low-temperature CMS. Even
441 though at an early stage of development, the coated reactor addresses the major
442 challenge of carbon clogging, displaying a promising configuration in terms of
443 scalability and long-term hydrogen production from catalytic methane splitting at low
444 temperatures. The production rate of this reactor is directly related to the catalytic
445 surface and indirectly to the volume of the reactor. The scalability of this reactor
446 configuration can be accomplished by increasing the area of the catalytic film while
447 maintaining a catalyst-to-reactor volume ratio large enough to accommodate carbon
448 formation. The substrates used to increase film area can be tubular or planar, depending
449 on the optimal structure to accommodate a larger catalyst amount without
450 compromising operation by clogging. The stacking design, pressure-drop, mass transfer
451 limitations, energy and mass injection, and hydrodynamics can be improved by
452 controlling parameters like catalyst particle size, layer thickness, or hydrodynamic
453 diameter (distance between catalytic substrates) [40]. Additionally, it was possible to
454 apply gasification strategies at the carbon-catalyst interface for catalyst regeneration
455 and carbon removal [4,41]. Since the catalyst is immobilized on a substrate, it is

456 possible to remove carbon while maintaining the catalyst active and continuous
457 operation.

Table 4 - Summary of the results obtained for all reactors tested

Exp.	Reactor configuration	Catalyst		Feed		t (h)	Residence time (s)	Conversion (%)		Activity ($\frac{\text{g}_{\text{H}_2}}{\text{g}_{\text{cat}} \cdot \text{h}}$)			Carbon ($\text{g}_{\text{C}} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$)
		Amount (mg)	Loading ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	Flowrate ($\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)	GHSV ($\text{L} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)			Initial	Final	Initial	Final	Average	
1	Fixed Bed (Reactor I)	500	n.a.	10	1.2	1.8	15	24	24	0.05	0.05	0.053	0.3
2	Fluidized Bed (Reactor II)	500	n.a.	20	2.4	4.2	15	18	20	0.08	0.09	0.082	1.1
3	Wall Coated (Reactor III)	500	23.9	20	2.4	11	15	22	22	0.10	0.10	0.095	3.2
4	Wall Coated (Reactor III)	408	19.5	175	25.7	2.3	2	19	12	0.88	0.57	0.725	4.9
5	Wall Coated (Reactor III)	235	11.2	175	44.7	2.2	2	19	12	1.50	0.98	1.240	8.0
6	Tubular Coated (Reactor IV)	310	19.7	100	19.4	46.4	19	19	3	0.67	0.10	0.385	62.0
7	Tubular Coated (Reactor IV)	266	16.9	125	28.2	21.5	15	18	3	0.91	0.15	0.530	47.0
8	Tubular Coated (Reactor IV)	287	18.3	175	36.6	16.9	11	18.5	2.3	1.22	0.15	0.685	48.0
9	Tubular Coated (Reactor IV)	165	10.5	175	63.6	8.8	11	23	1.3	2.65	0.15	1.400	43.0
10	Tubular Coated (Reactor IV)	346	22.0	175	30.3	18.9	11	20	2.7	1.10	0.15	0.625	48.0
11	Plate Coated (Reactor V)	39	7.8	50	76.9	2	6	7.1	0.33	1.00	0.05	0.525	1.4

459 n.a. - not applicable

460 3.2 *Morphological Characterization*

461 The carbon produced was analyzed to assess the presence of the metal catalyst and
462 to assess its crystallinity. Additionally, samples from the catalyst layer were also
463 analyzed. The thermogravimetric analysis under air flow of the two types of samples is
464 displayed in Figure 7a), in this case, from the carbon produced in Experiment 6.
465 Amorphous carbon starts oxidizing at 400 °C, while graphite and other highly ordered
466 carbon materials are oxidized at 700 - 800 °C. A very sharp mass loss is observed at *ca.*
467 550 °C, indicating the presence of ordered carbon materials in both samples, most
468 probably turbostratic carbon [42–44]. The catalyst layer sample shows a small mass
469 loss at 550 °C, indicating that most of the material in the layer is the metal catalyst. On
470 the other hand, the carbon sample displays a stable residual mass, probably related to
471 detached metal catalyst particles. The XRD diffractograms for the carbon and *post-*
472 *mortem* catalytic layer are shown in Figure 7b). The diffractogram of the catalyst
473 sample indicates the presence of nickel and α -Al₂O₃, which should be assigned to the
474 sample collection process by scraping the alumina substrate, since no alumina peaks
475 were detected in the XRD diffractogram of the pristine catalyst [45]; additionally, no
476 carbon signal was detected. On the other hand, the XRD diffractogram of the detached
477 carbon indicates the presence of nickel and carbon. The presence of nickel suggests, to
478 some extent, the tip-growth mechanism of carbon, with the consequent loss of catalyst
479 from the substrate [46].

480

481 Figure 7 - Thermogravimetric analysis (a) and XRD diffractograms (b) of the carbon
 482 (black line) and *post-mortem* catalytic layer samples (blue line).

483 Figure 8 showcases SEM images of the detached carbon samples from experiments
 484 performed with Reactor IV. Images 8b) and 8e), as well as 8c) and 8f), were captured
 485 from the same locations. Figures 8b) and 8c) were taken using the secondary electron

486 detector, while Figures 8e) and 8f) were obtained with the backscattered electron
487 detector. Even though the *post-mortem* catalytic substrates from Reactor IV display a
488 defect-free catalytic layer (Figure S4 in SI), it is possible to observe in Figure 8a) and
489 d) large agglomerates of catalyst mixed with carbon samples. EDS analysis was
490 performed on the brighter and darker particles– Z1 and Z2 from Figure 8d),
491 respectively, confirming the presence of catalyst among the produced carbon; the
492 mechanical integrity of the layer is compromised by carbon growth. From Figure 8b)
493 and 8c), it is possible to observe a variety of carbon materials produced, ranging from
494 carbon nanofibers to amorphous carbon. A larger amount of amorphous carbon was
495 observed for the experiments with higher GHSV, indicating that higher reaction rates
496 produce less crystalline carbon particles. TEM images from the carbon samples show
497 filamentous carbon - Figure 9d) and 9e). However, the number of defects in the
498 structure of these filaments is considerable. Pear-shaped nickel tips, typically associated
499 with fishbone carbon nanofibers, were also observed in Figures 9b) and 9c). This
500 structure was the most commonly detected type of carbon filament in the obtained TEM
501 images. [47] Even though it is also present amorphous carbon particles with no
502 filamentous nature (Figure 9f), closer analysis (Z3) showcases considerable
503 crystallinity with graphite layer stacking being observed, similarly to turbostratic
504 carbon (Figure S7 from SI). Additionally, it is also possible to observe in Figure 9a) the
505 presence of catalyst agglomerates, which confirms the residual mass observed in the
506 TGA analysis (Figure 7a). This also corroborates that the catalyst detachment from the
507 substrate occurs mainly due to the absence of a binder in the ink formulation for the
508 deposition.

510 Figure 8 – SEM images of the carbon produced from several experiments using
 511 Reactor IV. EDS spectrograms of Z1 and Z2 can be found in SI. a) and d) large catalyst
 512 and carbon agglomerates; b) and e) carbon nanofibers; c) and f) amorphous carbon.

513

514 Figure 9 - TEM images of the carbon produced in the tubular coated reactor. A zoom-
 515 in of Z3 can be found in SI. a) catalyst agglomerate; b) and c) carbon nanofibers with
 516 nickel tips; d) and e) carbon nanofibers; f) turbostratic carbon.

517 Considering the sharp weight loss observed in the TGA, it can be concluded that,
 518 despite the very low quality of the carbon fibers, they have a similar crystallography.
 519 However, different reactor configurations produce slightly different carbon fibers.
 520 Different reaction conditions, namely, temperature [48] or space velocity [49], vary the

521 carbon formation rate, producing carbon materials with different morphologies. This
522 trend can be observed by comparing the carbon materials obtained from different
523 experiments. Figure 10 shows the Raman spectra, between 1000 cm^{-1} to 1800 cm^{-1} , of
524 carbon samples from several experiments. Deconvolution of the spectra using
525 Lorentzian functions to fit the obtained data was done considering the traditional D
526 (1340 cm^{-1}) and G (1580 cm^{-1}) peaks and three other first-order peaks commonly
527 reported in this range: D* (1180 cm^{-1}), D'' (1500 cm^{-1}) and D' (1610 cm^{-1}). [50] In the
528 experiments showcased in Figure 10, there is an increase in GHSV from $2.4\text{ L}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$
529 to $76.9\text{ L}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The increase in space velocity leads to an overall activity increase,
530 thus leading to an increased rate of carbon formation. The $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio for these
531 experiments is 1.58, 1.73, 1.92, 2.00, and 2.33 for Experiments 2, 3, 7, 9, and 11,
532 respectively. The increase in the $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio indicates the presence of more structural
533 defects in the carbon obtained with higher GHSV. From the industrial viewpoint,
534 carbon materials must also be valued to further improve the economics of this process.
535 Filamentous carbon materials have higher commercial value [51]; however, the
536 presence of metal catalyst should be avoided, and the reaction conditions should be
537 carefully controlled to obtain valuable carbon materials.

538

539 Figure 10 - Raman spectra of the carbon materials obtained in several experiments

540 **4. Conclusion**

541 Five reactor configurations were built and tested for the catalytic low-temperature
 542 methane splitting reaction: fixed (reactor I) and fluidized (reactor II) bed reactors, wall
 543 coated reactor (reactor III), tubular coated reactor (reactor IV), and plate coated reactor
 544 (reactor V). Commercial nickel catalyst supported in silica-alumina was deposited over

545 a stainless-steel surface (reactor III) and alumina surface (reactors IV and V) using an
546 ink made of a solvent – α -terpineol – and the catalyst. Results indicate that the new
547 proposed reactor configurations showcase similar results in terms of conversion and
548 mass transfer limitations to traditional reactor configurations; nevertheless, these new
549 configurations displayed no pressure build-up during operation. A catalyst-to-reactor
550 volume ratio lower than $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ was required to avoid clogging of the reactor.
551 Catalyst activity and stability are strongly dependent on operational parameters, with
552 experimental results indicating that full deactivation is also strongly dependent on the
553 normalized total carbon production. Carbon morphological characterization indicates
554 the presence of carbon nanofibers formed with a tip-growth mechanism, mainly in the
555 form of turbostratic carbon. Additionally, an increase in the catalyst activity was
556 correlated with the formation of less structured carbon.

557 Even though it was demonstrated at a small scale, these new reactor configurations
558 can showcase a promising design for low-temperature catalytic methane splitting
559 industrial reactor. For practical applications, the reactor design, the catalyst substrate,
560 and the catalyst binder to the substrate are as critical for reaction activity and stability
561 as the catalyst itself. These disruptive coated reactor configurations reveal opportunities
562 for the scale-up of this technology and also extend the lifetime of the catalyst by
563 promoting carbon separation from the reaction gases.

564 **Acknowledgements**

565 The authors acknowledge the European Commission through the European Union's
566 Horizon 2020 programme - FET Proactive research and innovation action - under grant

567 agreement No. 952219 (112CO2). This work was supported by national funds through
568 FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC): LEPABE, UIDB/00511/2020 (DOI:
569 10.54499/UIDB/00511/2020) and UIDP/00511/2020 (DOI:
570 10.54499/UIDP/00511/2020) and ALiCE, LA/P/0045/2020 (DOI:
571 10.54499/LA/P/0045/2020);
572 Vítor Pereira, Luís Alves and Paula Dias acknowledge the Portuguese Foundation
573 of Science and Technology (FCT) support for their grants - SFRH/BD/143218/2019,
574 2020.10008.BD and CEECIND/02862/2018, respectively.

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